

NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE. IMPACT OF PHYTOTECHNOLOGY ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT AND WATER RESOURCES**Smuleac L.***University of Life Sciences "King Michael I" from Timisoara, 119 C. Aradului, 300645 Timisoara, Romania***Davlatzoda S.***Higher Attestation Commission under the President of the Republic of Tajikistan., Republic of Tajikistan,**Dushanbe, 39 Shevchenko,***Pascalau R.***University of Life Sciences "King Michael I" from Timisoara, 119 C. Aradului, 300645 Timisoara, Romania***Jurakhonzoda R.***Tajik Technical University named after academician M.S.Osimi., Republic of Tajikistan, 734042, Dushanbe,**academicians Rajabov's avenue 10,***Qalandarbekov I.***Tajik Technical University named after academician M.S.Osimi., Republic of Tajikistan, 734042, Dushanbe,**academicians Rajabov's avenue 10,*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13788509>**Abstract**

The article presents the results of the study of physico-chemical and bacteriological indicators of wastewater using two hospitals in the Rudaki district, where a phyto-engineering facility was installed to treat the wastewater of these hospitals. The natural based technologies or phytotechnologies have become an alternative to conventional technologies due to low capital costs, low maintenance requirements and high internal sustainability. The problem of water quality in water supply sources and protection of water resources is becoming more and more urgent under conditions of constant deterioration of ecological situation in the world, including in our country, and strengthening of anthropogenic impact on the quality of life of the society. Every year the population density increases, and with it the level of environmental pollution by human wastes. The main sources of wastewater pollution are physiological discharges. The main sources of wastewater pollution are physiological excretions of humans and animals, as well as waste and garbage generated because of economic activity. The results of the analysis of the wastewater treatment system are presented.

Keywords: phytotechnologies, wastewater, water quality and water supply, ecological situation, environmental pollution.

INTRODUCTION

In the present circumstances of economic crisis, the majority of industrial enterprises and public institutions are experiencing a shortage of funds for the operation, modernization, and even more so for the construction of new high-tech wastewater treatment facilities (R. H. Kadlec, 2009). This leads to an insufficient degree of industrial and domestic wastewater treatment and increased negative impact on water resources and the environment. Since surface water reservoirs are the main receivers of wastewater, their protection from anthropogenic pollution is an actual problem. To solve this problem it makes sense to develop and improve efficient and cost-effective methods of additional treatment of domestic and industrial wastewater, etc (N.M.Shegolkova, V. Dias, E.A. Kriksunov, K.Y. Ribka, 2015).

The application of phytotechnology, which is a combination of science and engineering, involves the use of plants to prevent, reduce or restore wastewater existing in an ecosystem. Plants can also be use as indicators to monitor and assess ecosystem health (S.V.Yakovlev, Y.V. Voronov, 2004).

The problem of water quality in water supply sources and protection of water resources is becoming more and more urgent under conditions of constant deterioration of ecological situation in the world, including in Tajikistan, and strengthening of anthropogenic

impact on the quality of life of the society (A. Orkhan, 2022). Every year the population density increases, and with it the level of environmental pollution by human wastes. The main sources of wastewater pollution are physiological discharges. The main sources of wastewater pollution are physiological excretions of humans and animals, as well as waste and garbage generated because of economic activity (Y.Vystavna, Z.Frkova, L.Marchand, et.all, 2017).

With support from the Tajikistan Water Supply and Sanitation Project, a decentralized wastewater treatment system (DEWATS) for two hospitals was piloted in the peri-urban district of Rudaki to scale up to the national level (A. Orkhan, 2022).

Currently, there are more than 100 successfully functioning biological treatment facilities in the form of ponds of various designs in the Central Asian region. However, the most common type of sewage ponds are ponds designed for purification and additional treatment of wastewater. There are also biological ponds with higher aquatic vegetation that purifies the water (R. H. Kadlec, 2009). Studies conducted by Zaman, B., Samadikin, B.P., et.al. (2020), have shown that eucrophia, reeds and other aquatic plants can extract the following amounts of nutrients from the water: 550-670 kg of nitrogen, 230-270 kg of phosphorus, 390-415 kg of potassium and 200 kg of calcium from 1 hectare of area at a yield of 44 tons of dry matter per hectare.

Picture 1. Different types of phyto-cleaning systems

DEWATS reports that currently, Central Asian countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan have also started to use phyto-engineering facilities for wastewater treatment in social institutions, households and rural settlements.

In Tajikistan, pilot phyto-engineering facilities have been constructed in the peri-urban districts of Rudaki, Gissar and Aini, as well as in Spitamen district of Sughd province.

One of such projects on decentralized wastewater treatment system using phyto-engineering facility technology in Rudaki Central District Hospital was the object of research in the framework of the project "CoP4WASH in Central Asia", which is presented in Picture 1 (A. Orkhan, 2022).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The object of the study is located in two hospitals of Rudaki district equipped with sewage treatment plants. These facilities are designed to treat the entire generated volume of wastewater in these hospitals, which is then discharged into the canal and pollutes the underground aquifers.

Special liter vessels are used for sampling. After sampling, each vessel is disinfected with 70% ethanol to prevent further spread of biological contamination. The time, date and place of collection are recorded in a note. For example: (07.07.2024, 1 (septic outfall), 09:44). Primary analyses (Cond, pH, TDS, Salt, T-°C) are then performed using a Voltcraft instrument and pH meter.

Picture 2. Moments of sampling

All results obtained and stored in a work log. Samples are then transported in special temperature-controlled crates to the laboratory for further bacteriological

analyses: turbidity, ammonium, phosphate, chemical oxygen demand (COD) and bacteriological analysis (BAC).

Table 1. Data for selecting the type of wastewater treatment facilities published by Shegolkova, N.M., et.al. (2015)

Name of structures	Average daily wastewater flow rate, m ³ /day						
	up to 50	up to 300	up to 500	up to 10000	up to 30000	up to 50000	50000 above
Mechanical cleaning							
grilles	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Sand catchers							
vertical	-	-	+	+	+	-	-
horizontal	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
with circular water flow	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
Sumps							
double decker	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
vertical	-	-	-	X	X	X	-
horizontal	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
radial	-	-	-	X	+	+	+
digesters	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
sludge pads	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
vacuum filters	-	-	-	-	-	+	+

chlorator plants	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Biological treatment							
irrigation fields	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
filtration fields	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
biological ponds	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
biofilters	+	+	+	X	-	-	-
aerotanks	-	-	-	X	+	+	+
sludge thickeners	-	-	-	+	+	+	+

Notation:

- + - recommended;
- x - applied with appropriate justification;
- not recommended.

After the research and various samples were taken, discussions, debates and real-time analysis of the results are conducted.

Ammonium determination is carried out with all samples. Before starting, each sample is filtered. Then 2 mL of the waste water after filtration, 5 mL of ammonium and 1 portion of the reagent are added to the test tube as specified in the instructions. To prepare zero solution, 2 ml of distilled water, 5 ml of ammonium and 1 portion of the reagent are added to the test tube. For

the reaction to take place, it is necessary to wait 15 minutes. Zero solution differs from the rest by color: zero solution is yellowish, samples are dark green, blue.

All samples are also used for the determination of phosphate. For the analysis, 2.1 ml of phosphate and 5 ml of wastewater are added to the test tube. After sample preparation, the samples are tested on a spectrophotometric instrument and all data are recorded in the work log.

Picture 3. Ammonium and phosphate determinations

The device allows the following measurements: pH (mV), pH (pH); (COND) - conductivity; (TDS) - total solids dissolved in water; (SAL) - salinity expressed by conductivity; (turb) - turbidity; (TEMP) -

water temperature. The measurement results are stored in storage and can be processed by a computer using a special program.

Picture 4. Tests and assays that were performed in a laboratory setting (in the department lab).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

These analyses give reliable results on the concentration of chemical substances affecting organoleptic properties of water. The concentration of these substances in natural waters or added in the process of water treatment should not exceed the standards specified in Tables 2,3,4. Drinking water quality indicators must

comply with the Urban Planning Norms and Rules GNiP RT 40-06-2017 "Rural drinking water supply". Committee on Architecture and Construction under the Government of the Republic of Tajikistan, 2017, 48 pp. It can be seen from the figure that wastewater treatment with the help of this facility works efficiently and gives good result (K. Y. Ribka, 2020., A. Orkhan, 2022).

Table 2. Physical, chemical and microbiological analysis of collected samples - 1

Calculated results											
Sample	pH	cond [mS/cm]	TDS [ppt]	Salt [ppt]	Temp P [°C]	Turbidity [-]	PO4-P [mg/L]	Amonium [mg/L]	COD [mg/L]	E.Coli [CFU/ml]	Coliform [CFU/ml]
1 (septic tank - inlet)	7	1,221	1,001	0,888	16	-	19,8	-	-	-	-
2 (anaerobic reactor)	7	1,92	1,34	1,04	16	-	17,7	-	-	-	-
3 (anaerobic filter)	7	2,08	1,38	1,07	16	-	29,7	-	-	-	-
4 (anaerobic filter 2)	7	2,09	1,37	0,977	12	-	28,9	-	-	-	-
5 (outlet wetland)	7	1,954	1,37	1,04	14	-	24,1	-	-	-	-

Note: (-) no study on turbidity, PO4- P, Amonium, COD(COD), E.Coli, Coliform was carried out

Table 3. Physical, chemical and microbiological analysis of collected samples - 2

Calculated results											
Sample	pH	cond [mS/cm]	TDS [ppt]	Salt [ppt]	Temp [°C]	Turbidity [-]	PO4-P [mg/L]	Amonium [mg/L]	COD(XIHK) [mg/L]	E.Coli [CFU/ml]	Coliform [CFU/ml]
1 (septic tank - inlet)	7	1,184	1,34	1,04	30,1	54	31,3	130,8	254	361	192
2 (anaerobic reactor)	7	2	1,33	1,02	29,5	101	33	111,2	-	-	-
3 (anaerobic filter)	7	1,97	1,331	1,112	28,2	114	29,2	164,1	-	-	-
4 (anaerobic filter 2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 (outlet wetland)	7	1,8	1,3	0,991	27,9	220	27,6	112,2	70	80	48

Table 4. Physical, chemical and microbiological analysis of collected samples - 3

Calculated results											
Sample	pH	cond [mS/cm]	TDS [ppt]	Salt [ppt]	Temp [°C]	Turbidity [-]	PO4-P [mg/L]	Amonium [mg/L]	COD(XIHK) [mg/L]	E.Coli [CFU/ml]	Coliform [CFU/ml]
1 (septic tank - inlet)	7	0,117	0,796	0,58	28,2	55	28,4	93,4	258	226	135
2 (anaerobic reactor)	7	1,911	1,296	0,98	27,3	64	28,22	101,5	-	-	-
3 (anaerobic filter)	7	0,209	0,18	0,15	26,8	84	27,3	185,4	-	-	-
4 (anaerobic filter 2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 (outlet wetland)	7	1,865	1,261	0,957	25,3	158	19,9	154,6	64	85	56

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, we are utilizing these different physiological properties of plants to develop new environmentally sustainable strategies to solve social, environmental

and engineering problems. Alternatives to conventional/centralized wastewater treatment systems are required to meet the high demand in peri-urban and urban areas (e.g. townships), within an acceptable budget and

period. This is because conventional solutions (extensive sewer networks with large centralized treatment plants) are quite time-consuming to implement and very often exceed the available funds.

Decentralized or partially centralized systems are a viable alternative, are highly flexible and can be easily adapted to local needs and basic conditions. Particularly in urban and peri-urban areas, non-traditional decentralized sanitation control systems have proven to be sustainable and cost-effective solutions in many developing countries.

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